

Guiding Deep Learning with Landscape Metrics for LULC Mapping Applications

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Abstract

Deep Learning (DL) has become a core methodology in GeoAI and remote sensing, yet many models still lack explicit integration of geographic principles, often leading to computationally expensive and geographically implausible predictions. This work investigates how geographic knowledge can be integrated into deep learning models as a regularization signal. Using landscape metrics derived from OpenStreetMap, we show that these metrics capture structural similarities and differences across regions and can serve as transferable geographic references. We propose a two head architecture based on SegFormer, combining semantic segmentation with a regression head that predicts landscape metrics from the segmentation output. A composite loss integrates cross entropy with a landscape metrics based regularization term to guide training. Initial experiments demonstrate stable convergence while highlighting challenges in computational efficiency and loss design. Overall, this work represents a first step toward GIScience-guided DL, emphasizing spatial structure and geographic context for more interpretable and sustainable models.

Keywords: giscience-guided deep learning, landscape metrics, remote sensing, LULC, OpenStreetMap

1. Context and Motivation

DL has become a core methodological pillar in remote sensing and GeoAI, enabling large-scale applications such as Land Use Land Cover (LULC) mapping, object detection, and spatiotemporal prediction. Despite impressive performance gains, current DL models often operate with limited integration of geographic principles, leading to high computational demands and outputs

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that lack logical spatial consistency (S. Zhao et al. 2023; T. Zhao et al. 2024). This becomes particularly evident in heterogeneous or transitional landscapes, where models such as transformers may generate geographically inconsistent patterns that conflict with known spatial structures or processes. These limitations challenge model generalization, interpretability, and transferability across regions, highlighting the need for GIScience-guided DL approaches that explicitly account for geographic context and constraints (Ge et al. 2022; T. Zhao et al. 2024).

In LULC mapping, humans can often easily detect misclassifications even without domain expertise, as they integrate spatial context and other intuitive observations of geographic objects. This knowledge of spatial relations, which can be summarized as geographic knowledge (Ge et al. 2022), is often probabilistic, context-dependent, and scale-sensitive rather than deterministic. As a result, it cannot be directly used in DL models, which require differentiable information.

To address this gap, we propose a method for integrating geographic knowledge in the form of expected landscape patterns as regularization parameters into an image-based DL model. In the context of LULC mapping, semantically similar regions are expected to share structural characteristics that can be transferred across areas (Wiens et al. 1993; Niesterowicz, Stepinski 2016). Landscape metrics (Turner 1989), initially developed for ecological applications, quantify these structural patterns, offering a natural, machine-readable representation of geographic knowledge. In this study, we leverage these metrics by integrating them into a DL architecture for LULC mapping. Our focus is on exploring methods to incorporate this geographic knowledge into model training and assessing its impact on both the performance and efficiency of DL models.

2. Methodological Approach

Using counties in southwest Germany as semantically similar regions and Holland in the Netherlands as a contrasting control, we divided the areas of interest into uniformly sized rectangular patches. For each patch, multiple class-level landscape metrics were computed from OpenStreetMap data, with ten out of twenty-two selected for suitability and interpretability. The resulting metric distributions were compared using distributional and distance-based measures. The initial analysis confirmed that these metrics capture structural similarities and differences between regions, motivating their use not only as descriptive measures of landscape similarity (Niesterowicz, Stepinski 2016), but as an explicit source of geographic knowledge that can be integrated into model training.

To operationalize this idea, we embedded landscape metrics as a regularization term into a flexible SegFormer architecture (Xie et al. 2021) for LULC mapping, allowing them to directly influence the learning process (Burgert et al. 2026). This was achieved by using a two-head architecture, extending the SegFormer segmentation head by an additional regression head. The first head performs standard semantic segmentation on multiband raster imagery as input and produces per-pixel class probabilities \hat{Y} using a categorical cross-entropy loss \mathcal{L}_{CE} . The second head takes the segmentation output as input and passes it through a lightweight feedforward network $f_{FFN}(\cdot)$ to predict select landscape metrics. These predicted metrics are compared to reference metrics q^{LSM} from a similar region using a difference measure Δ , resulting in a landscape metrics-based regularization term that injects geographic knowledge into the training process (Dialameh et al. 2024;

Niesterowicz, Stepinski 2016). The regularization term, thereby, is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Reg}} = \Delta\left(f_{\text{FFN}}(\hat{\mathbf{Y}}) \parallel \mathbf{q}^{\text{LSM}}\right), \quad (1)$$

The overall training objective is a weighted combination of the standard cross-entropy loss and the landscape-based regularization term:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} + \lambda \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{Reg}}, \quad (2)$$

where the weighting factor λ controls the relative contribution of the landscape metrics-based regularization to the total loss. This formulation ensures that gradients from the regularization term propagate through the second head back to the segmentation output, allowing landscape structure to influence model learning as a soft constraint.

To avoid overloading the model and maintain efficiency, we selected the five most important metrics via feature importance analysis across multiple areas of interest. Reference landscape metrics were computed from the county of Karlsruhe, Germany, and prepared in multiple formats to support different regularization strategies: (1) as class-wise average values with tensor broadcasting, compatible with moment-based losses such as MSE; (2) by randomly sampling from kernel density estimates (KDE) of per-patch metric distributions, yielding a more diverse reference dataset than using means alone; and (3) as full distributional representations using the KDE directly, enabling regularization with divergence metrics such as Kullback-Leibler (KL) and Jensen-Shannon (JS) divergence. Since some landscape metrics have unbounded ranges, we applied z-score normalization where necessary.

The differences between predicted and prepared metrics were integrated into the model as a regularization term, as described above, introducing an additional loss to the overall objective function. To evaluate its impact, we tested the weighting factor λ at values of 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, and 1.0. These experiments were compared to a baseline model that used only the initial loss term without the second regression head. This comparison allowed the assessment of both the performance impact of the regularization and its computational efficiency, as the second head and additional operations, such as constructing the KDE, introduce extra computational overhead.

3. Initial Results

The initial analysis of landscape metrics shows that they effectively capture the landscape characteristics of both similar and contrasting regions (see figure 1). In most cases, the metric distributions of the Dutch control differ noticeably from those of the German counties, which exhibit the expected higher degree of similarity.

The structural similarity was quantified using distributional and distance-based measures across twenty landscape metrics. Averaged over all metrics, the results show consistently higher similarity among the German counties and clear divergence from the Dutch control (see table 1), support-

Figure 1: Two example class-level landscape metrics illustrating similarities and differences in the metrics across areas of interest. Landscape Shape Index quantifies the complexity of patch shapes in a landscape, with higher values indicating more irregular and convoluted patch boundaries.

ing their use as a reference in our regularization approach. Across the shown similarity metrics, Stuttgart is more similar to the baseline than Freiburg, with the exception of the KL divergence, suggesting a metric-specific deviation that warrants further investigation.

Table 1: Similarity to the county of Karlsruhe was quantified by averaging JS, KL, Wasserstein Distance (WS), and Kolmogorov–Smirnov Test (KS) scores across all selected landscape metrics. The lower the value, the more similar to the baseline.

Area of Interest	JS	KL	WS	KS
County of Freiburg	0.1	0.74	9.94e+08	0.21
County of Stuttgart	0.08	1.37	4.29e+08	0.14
Holland (Control)	0.38	5.81	8.92e+09	0.59

Preliminary experiments on a subregion of the county of Karlsruhe, including the cities Mannheim and Heidelberg as well as the district Rhein-Neckar-Kreis, indicated that all proposed methods achieved convergence. However, this came at the cost of a sometimes substantial increase in computation time and a reduction in model performance. In a few cases, performance matched the baseline, but it never surpassed it. Conversely, some training runs required fewer epochs to reach convergence compared to the baseline, suggesting an increase in the information density available for the model to learn from.

The initial implementation, which used a broadcasted reference tensor and an MSE loss, achieved convergence but compared predicted landscape metrics only against global mean values. This resulted in a coarse and weakly informative regularization signal at the patch level, leading to longer runtimes and reduced overall performance. However, certain classes did show improved accuracy, indicating that some regularization signals were beneficial for training.

The second method, which randomly sampled values from the KDE, exhibited similar behavior. The results were more balanced, with less extreme variation; some classes decreased in accuracy

while others improved. Still, the specific impact of the regularization on the model remains an open question for further investigation.

The divergence-based loss, using KL and JS divergences with full distributional representations from the KDE, is currently only implemented on a basic level. While it showed improved performance compared to the first two methods, it still fell short of the baseline, due to missing optimization and the need to handle small batch sizes caused by the framework’s architecture and resource demands. Nevertheless, this approach is expected to provide a more informative training signal by comparing full metric distributions rather than single summary values. This is anticipated to improve gradient quality and optimization efficiency during training, potentially reducing runtime while yielding more geographically consistent predictions.

4. Impact and Implications

This work presents a first step toward guiding DL models with landscape-related geographic knowledge integrated directly into the training process as a regularization signal. By transferring this knowledge across semantically similar regions, the approach aims to promote geographically plausible predictions and improved consistency in LULC mapping. Building on this idea, the framework could support the generation of more detailed LULC maps in regions with sparse OpenStreetMap or reference data by leveraging information from structurally similar landscapes. Existing global products and representations, such as coarse global LULC datasets or embeddings from foundational models, already provide ways to identify similar landscapes and could serve as valuable sources for this knowledge transfer. In addition, the framework could be applied to assess the quality of LULC data from sources such as OpenStreetMap, since the employed landscape metrics are human readable and interpretable. Demonstrating a concrete implementation of GIScience-guided DL, this work illustrates how geographic principles such as spatial structure, scale, and semantic similarity can be incorporated to support more efficient, interpretable, and sustainable AI for geospatial applications.

Future work will focus on optimizing the regularization architecture and exploring alternative strategies for sampling the reference distribution, including Markov chain Monte Carlo methods, batch stacking to improve the detail and representativeness of the distributions, and weighted combinations of methods within the regularization term. Additional experiments, including ablation studies, are planned to evaluate the impact of individual landscape metrics on the difference calculation and to investigate their sensitivity across spatial scales, potentially motivating metric-specific weighting within the loss function. Although operational optimizations reduced the computational overhead to a negligible level, the regression head and regularization term still require further streamlining and optimization. Their impact on the training process therefore remains a key focus of future research within this project. Additionally, once the experimental setup has been fully validated, we aim to scale the approach to larger regions and more diverse landscapes in order to evaluate its generalizability and robustness across different geographic contexts.

While this study uses landscape similarity as a practical test case, geographic knowledge extends far beyond this single aspect. Effectively defining, quantifying, and encoding such knowledge within DL frameworks requires careful thresholding, loss design, and architectural decisions, while

also accounting for spatial heterogeneity and varying quality of OpenStreetMap and other reference datasets. As demonstrated by the regularization strategies explored in this work, designing loss functions that meaningfully evaluate geographic knowledge integration remains an open challenge and an important direction for future research.

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